

Tool	Dataset	Detected clones			Operation time			
		BC	PC	Delta	BC	PC Raw	PC Optimized	Delta (PC Optimized / BC)
SourcererCC	Smaller	35,836	50,356	40.5%	3 min 12 sec	19 min 12 sec	18 min 38 sec	482%
	Larger	136,591	193,411	41.6%	10 min 59 sec	32 min 12 sec	28 min 07 sec	156%
CloneWorks	Smaller	20,172	31,584	56.6%	26 sec	38 sec	34 sec	31%
	Larger	27,309	40,955	50%	3 min 58 sec	4 min 29 sec	4 min 20 sec	9%

Table I
THE RESULTS OF THE PROJECTS-BASED EVALUATION.
BC STANDS FOR BEST SINGLE-THRESHOLD CONFIGURATION, PC STANDS FOR PARAMETRIC CURVE.

Table II
SOURCERERCC — SMALLER DATASET.

Stage	No optimization		Optimization	
	Time, s	Pairs	Time, s	Pairs
Tokenization	49	—	49	—
ST 75	143	35,836	134	14,342
ST 73	148	32,038	134	18,036
ST 71	138	23,931	133	10,620
ST 70	139	23,922	134	20,346
ST 65	134	13,055	134	10,819
ST 60	134	10,026	134	9,998
ST 55	134	456	133	442
ST 50	133	55	133	55
Merging	< 1	—	< 1	—
Total	1,152	139,319	1,118	84,658
Unique:	50,356	50,356	50,356	50,356

Table IV
CLONERWORKS — SMALLER DATASET.

Stage	No optimization		Optimization	
	Time, s	Pairs	Time, s	Pairs
Tokenization	23.8	—	23.8	—
ST 77	2	19,500	1.1	7,065
ST 75	2.1	18,389	1.2	5,599
ST 72	2	20,172	1.3	9,439
ST 71	2	15,879	1.2	7,542
ST 70	2	14,045	1.5	10,762
ST 65	1.8	10,172	1.5	9,224
ST 60	1.3	4,289	1.1	4,260
ST 55	0.9	250	0.9	250
Merging	0.2	—	0.1	—
Total	38.1	102,696	33.7	54,138
Unique:	31,584	31,584	31,584	31,584

Table III
SOURCERERCC — LARGER DATASET.

Stage	No optimization		Optimization	
	Time, s	Pairs	Time, s	Pairs
Tokenization	470	—	470	—
ST 75	212	128,394	146	37,679
ST 73	198	129,479	148	106,968
ST 71	186	127,758	145	105,886
ST 70	189	136,591	151	131,292
ST 65	181	16,394	145	11,636
ST 60	209	9,826	197	9,479
ST 55	144	1,241	143	1,098
ST 50	142	470	142	470
Merging	1	—	< 1	—
Total	1,932	550,153	1,687	404,508
Unique:	193,411	193,411	193,411	193,411

Table V
CLONERWORKS — LARGER DATASET.

Stage	No optimization		Optimization	
	Time, s	Pairs	Time, s	Pairs
Tokenization	233	—	233	—
ST 77	5.1	27,309	3.1	12,863
ST 75	4.9	22,833	3.1	6,466
ST 72	5	25,250	3.5	15,259
ST 71	4.7	21,131	3.5	18,140
ST 70	4.6	16,071	3.5	14,795
ST 65	4.3	3,806	3.6	2,955
ST 60	3.8	1,944	3.1	1,797
ST 55	3.2	583	3.1	583
Merging	0.3	—	0.2	—
Total	268.9	118,927	260.2	72,858
Unique:	40,955	40,955	40,955	40,955